

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ABIYO****FIRST NAME: ABNET****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied * US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

I used MSWord 2010

1. Writing an academic essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 15)
3. American Vs. British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 33)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 40)
6. CMS CRIB sheet (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 43)
7. Latin Abbreviation and expressions (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 58)

PROFESSIONAL PAPER WRITING BASICS

1) INTRODUCTION

It was my first time attending online study at a higher level like this. Honestly, it was not clear how to start writing a response paper for the whole course but the road map given by EUCLID helped me to be on the right path. Academic writing course is a basic thing we need to comply with before conducting research. I found this course is a foundation for academic writing persuade throughout my Ph.D. study.

All chapters presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma in 2021 in the ACA-401D course are well explained. The course takes the reader deep into each chapter to understand the basics and acceptable standards of academic essays. The tips for essay writing have fed the reader with additional information. I learned that even simple punctuation would matter the whole meaning of the sentence. The course appreciated the similarities and differences between American and British English. Also, the course writers have given enough attention to the principles of plagiarism, how to avoid it, and the recommended way of citation. Most importantly I am convinced to steak with the recommended style of writing and referencing consistently.

This response paper addressed seven main topics: writing the essay, punctuation, American Vs. British English, Plagiarism, style guide, CMS CRIB sheet, and Latin Abbreviation and expression.

2) WRITING THE ESSAY

The course pack of ACA-401/401D clearly described how to write the essay. The steps, tips, and techniques of essay writing are discussed in this section, starting from scratch. I found the chapter very important as it contains basic academic writing skills. Moreover, understanding this chapter has given me confidence while I dream of writing an academic essay.

As the name indicates, an academic essay is one of the essay types commonly used for academic purposes. Obviously, like other essays, academic writings have their common characteristics" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7).

I realized that essay writing needs adequate time. Therefore, early starting to write the essay will give me a chance to read and re-write the academic essay. Even though there is no hard and fast rule for starting an academic essay, this chapter advises the readers to start timely, defining the key question and plotting the preliminary plan to follow. It is known that the research answer highly depends on the information we are using according to our predefined plan.

Once a writer understands the topic to write about, the next important thing is reading and researching what to write. Reading and researching will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 8). While reading and researching, we should critically think about the interest of knowledge and the relevance of the materials with the research topic that we are using. Focusing on the research topic the writer needs to look at various sources of information useful to organize the idea. While reading the credibility of the information source also needs to be considered. After we have a concrete idea about the topic in mind, we can start writing a draft. The draft should follow the common essay writing steps, like an introduction, a body, and finally, a conclusion.

EUCLID recommended CMS to reference the information we used in the academic essay. However, I realized EUCLID would also accept any form of referencing format if used strictly and consistently (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 11).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

In this chapter, I learned that punctuations are critical in scientific writing. "Punctuation consists of both rules and conventions. There are rules of punctuation that have to be followed, but there are also punctuation conventions that give writers greater choice" (Cambridge Dictionary 2023). ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack provided sample punctuation marks to show how to use by comparing the correct and incorrect punctuations.

Also, the ACA-401D guideline advises using as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning (16); for example, using apostrophes will completely change the sentence's meaning just because of the position where a writer used it. Various forms of brackets namely round brackets, square brackets, angle brackets, and curly brackets have their positions recommended to be used. The common errors we make while we use punctuation may distort the meaning of the sentences. The use of bullet points and other punctuation in the bullet points is well discussed in this chapter. Using a semicolon links two related parts of a sentence, neither of which depends logically on the other and each of which could stand alone as a grammatically complete sentence. Also, using a colon introduces a sub-clause that follows logically from the text before it (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 18).

It is not easy to distinguish the application of dashes and hyphens which symbolically mimic each other and are confusing. Commonly we use full stops, exclamation, question marks, and other punctuations in our daily writings. I found that it is very important to give enough attention to punctuation as they have a critical role in the clarity of the information. Knowing basic punctuation rules will save us from distorting the idea that we want to describe.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I was so amazed when I read about how American English has grown very fast and influenced the world following the political, economic, technological, and cultural upper hand. ACA-401D guideline described that American English has currently the dominant influence on "world English" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25). In addition to the grammatical, vocabulary, punctuation, and other variations, there are Ethnoleets and regional variations. I was always confused hearing some black Americans' English words which are not found in the dictionary. After reading this chapter, I realized such words are neither American nor British English but have their influence in English. Also, the current globalization has brought us some new English words related to the use of computers and new technologies. This may alarm us that new words still will be added to English as technology advances. The chapter also justified the similarity of both English weigh than the differences.

I believe knowing the difference between both English will help us not to mix up while we write, and rather it is important to use one of them consistently.

5) PLAGIARISM

All scholars agree that plagiarism is unethical and should be avoided. The word plagiarism is come from Kidnapping and is defined as an act or instance of plagiarizing. "The first known use of plagiarism was in 1621" (Merriam-Webster 2023) of course, plagiarism may happen intentionally or unintentionally. There is a good solution for plagiarism which is called a citation. Even though there are multiple citation styles in

academic writing, we should strictly follow only one citation style throughout research writing. Many institutions preferred specific referencing styles just for some reason. Therefore, it would be better to comply with the referencing style the academic institution recommends. The ACA-401D course pack provided instruction on how to quote the word, phrase, sentence, or paragraph according to their size and state. This is very useful information to all writers, even outside of EUCLID. It is common for all writers to use the findings of other scholars' findings, but we should not forget to give credit to the owner of the finding or the quoted idea we used. If we fail to do this will lose the credibility of the essay and fall under the judgment of plagiarism.

One thing I learned that is challenging while referencing is deciding whether to cite or not. Some ideas are very familiar and available in many writings for those who deal with the subject matter. But the same idea could be uncommon for a new writer unfamiliar with the topic. I believe this may cause some confusion to many writers, especially beginners.

6) STYLE GUIDE

The style guide is an uncommon but very interesting chapter in this guideline. Even though many scholars mention the main points discussed in this topic, it is not familiar to present as an independent topic organized like this. "A style guide is defined as "A means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41).

Turabian style of writing is emphasized as a recommended style at Euclid University. I believe this course will give me a chance to become familiar with this style of writing. As discussed in the previous section of American Vs. In British English, there are variations in punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary but the style guide will allow writers to address variations even beyond. Also, a style guide will make the writers more consistent throughout the writing. Moreover, the style guide enables the writer to focus on the main research idea rather than swinging from one style to another.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

All academic writings have a standard and acceptable form of referencing the source of information. Euclid University recommends Chicago manual style. "Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press)" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 44).

This chapter discussed the utilization of abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, various marks, and quotes recommended in the Chicago manual style. In academic writings, headings and the listing also have their style. Examples in this chapter also discuss an optional way of table presentation.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATION AND EXPRESSIONS

This chapter presented common Latin Abbreviations we used in daily writing formally and informally. The chapter advised avoiding the use of abbreviations in plain English as they may cause misinterpretation. In formal writing, using equivalent English instead of abbreviations is advised. However, it is possible to use Latin abbreviations in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 59). The List of Latin Abbreviations and expressions presented in this chapter may serve as a reference to utilize accordingly.

9) CONCLUSION

I found this course pack very interesting and contained critically important sections of academic writing. The basic principles of good writing are presented in different chapters in an organized way. The writers of ACA-401D used simple and understandable English. The videos in the course pack are also very important and focused on the main points, but I would prefer the speed of the speakers to be a bit slower. I believe they will consider the suggestion for the next videos.

I am surprised to read new chapters and styles in this course. I had exposure to writing research papers a couple of times, but I never came across with Guide style as well as the Turabian style. I liked the way the guideline were presented. All chapters have their inputs to equip the readers with the basic knowledge, principles, and skills of academic writing. Surely someone who properly attended this course will be a consistent and good writer. I got some level of confidence for my Ph.D. study when I went through this course. I recommend all academic writers read this chapter with due attention before writing an essay.

REFERENCES

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